

FABRICATION AND A REVIEW ON THE USAGE OF AQUASILENCER

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Abstract:

Fossil fuels such as coal, oil and natural gas are very useful and important energy sources. The environment comes at a price, so it's important to understand the sources and chemicals that pollute and how to minimize their impact. Pollutants from fossil fuels (coal, oil, gas, etc.) burning in power plants and automobiles include carbon monoxide, sulfur oxides, nitrogen oxides, and photochemical reactions that produce ozone and other noxious irritants. may generate From catalytic converters in automobiles to desulfurization of petroleum-based fuels and flue gases, pollution reduction methods are described. Diesel engines, among fossil fuels, play an important role in road, marine transportation, agriculture, mining and many other industries. Also, as mentioned above, there are some problems caused by pollution caused by diesel engines, mainly due to industry. This project is an attempt to reduce the level of pollutants in diesel engine exhaust before it is released into the atmosphere. Also, the systems we develop can be used in diesel generators that can be used in combustible atmospheres such as refineries, chemical processing industries, open pit mines and other enclosed areas. And the name we're developing suggests that, as the name suggests, it acts on a water medium that aids chemical reactions and helps reduce the noise produced by the engine.

Keywords — : Aquasilencer, photochemical reactions, catalytic converters, open pit mines.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main principle of the aqua silencer is to blow the exhaust gas into a cleaning tank containing an alkaline solution. Here, the temperature of the gas is lowered while removing most of the nitrogen oxides in the exhaust gas.

The first step can be safely done with an aqueous solution. The primary reaction is carried out and the temperature is lowered to an appropriate level. The most important thing about this alkaline solution is the reduction of sound propagating through various media. Silencer, as the name suggests. A container inside the scrubber tank contains calcium oxide (CaO). Several reactions within the container significantly reduce the proportion of pollutants in the exhaust gas. Here the main reaction takes place.

Therefore, it helps reduce toxic gases in diesel engine exhaust and reduce pollution. The water silencer is attached to the exhaust port of the engine as shown below. From the diagram you can see that the engine's exhaust manifold is the inlet for the aqua muffler. Then, the exhaust gas that enters the aqua muffler undergoes a chemical reaction and is released into the atmosphere from the aqua muffler. To measure the exhaust gas content, a sample is taken between the engine outlet and the scrubber outlet. This helps to know the performance of aqua muffler in diesel engine exhaust. Measured the difference in exhaust gas with and without the aqua silencer.

II. SCOPE OF THE WORK

It can be used for diesel generators used in flammable atmospheres such as refineries, chemical processing industries, open pit mines, power plants, industrial waste incineration, industrial processing and other enclosed areas. I am mainly in charge of exhaust gas regulations and noise countermeasures. Noise and smoke levels are significantly lower than traditional silencers. It's cheap and doesn't require a catalytic convert

III. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Engine exhaust backpressure is defined as the exhaust pressure generated by the engine to overcome the hydraulic resistance of the exhaust system in order to expel the gases to the atmosphere. Some of the factors that affect back pressure and engine performance are discussed below.

1. Exhaust manifold design
2. Valve overlap amount
3. Engine speed
4. number of cylinders
5. Exhaust gas passage length, etc.

Back pressure represented by the water in the tank;

The gas should push the water out and bubble the water in the wash tank. This can lead to increased back pressure.

Back pressure applied by BAFLES.

Baffles provided to divert exhaust gases also resist flow and increase internal back pressure.

Back pressure due to vaporized water particles;

Steam increases the net mass of the exhaust stream per unit time. This can lead to increased back pressure. Back pressure applied by limestone ships. Limestone containers are used to store limestone and offer greatly increased flow resistance which increases back pressure. Originally, limestone was supposed to break down the toxic components in the exhaust gas through a chemical reaction.

Back pressure applied by the length of the exhaust flow path;

The scrubber also increases the net length of the exhaust gas flow path, creating back pressure. Since the scrubber tank itself acts as a muffler and completely eliminates the resistance caused by another muffler, the system should be designed to reduce the back pressure increase mentioned above.

Bell effect - the mouth of the wash container.

The introduction of the funnel arrangement facilitates the gradual expansion of the exhaust gas to many times its volume before contacting the water in the scrubber tank. The process itself contributes to the pressure drop across the system.

IV. CONSTRUCTIONAL FEATURES

The aqua silencer consists of separate parts. This structure helps reduce the level of noise and pollutants in the exhaust by supporting the reaction. The engine's exhaust manifold is the inlet to the scrubber tank or aqua muffler. The exhaust from the engine then enters the wash tank and has several reactions that are released into the atmosphere.

SCRUBBER – TANK ASSEMBLY

The scrubber tank is built in 3 stages and includes the following subassemblies:

1 tank. 2. Bell - Mouth. 3. Limestone tank. 4. Level plug-drain assembly

IV.1 BELL MOUTH

Funnels are used to carry the exhaust gases leaving the engine. And shape is important to reduce noise and back pressure. The hopper outlet is approximately 2.5 times the area of the inlet. The exhaust gas expands and cools the gas. After expansion, the pressure drops and the emissions come into contact with water or alkali. The funnel

also provides more effective cooling due to the larger contact area with the water. It shows the importance of the funnel when using the aqua silencer.

FIG.1 BELL MOUTH

IV.2. LIME STONE CONTAINER

This diagram shows a limestone container used to collect limestone. It consists of a series of holes that aid in the flow of exhaust gases. Several reactions take place in this vessel. It is the main part of the aqua silencer that helps reduce toxic fumes.

FIG.2 LIMESTONE CONTAINER

IV.3. TANK

The tank is the supporting part of the aqua silencer. It contains water and alkaline solutions (lime water) that help the reactions and various processes in the Aqua Silencer. And that's the solid support of the whole system. This tank is fitted with a funnel mouth, a CaO reservoir, and a level plug drain assembly.

FIG.3 TANK COVER

IV.2. ASSEMBLY OF AQUASILENCER

FIG.4 ASSEMBLY OF AQUA SILENCER

V. WORKING PRINCIPLE

FIG.5 SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM OF AQUASILENCER

Exhaust gases from the engine reach the water silencer through the engine's exhaust manifold. The exhaust manifold is connected to the funnel as shown. All gas is forced through the funnel into the aqua silencer. The area of the bell mouth exit is entrance. This expands the exhaust gases and cools the gases. No energy can be released by expansion, helping adiabatic expansion in the funnel to cool. After expansion in the hopper, the pressure is reduced to an optimum level. Emissions also come into contact with water or alkaline solutions. The bell mouth has a large surface area on the base, which increases the contact surface with the water. Effective cooling occurs due to the large contact area. Exhaust gases are then bubbled through the water as it touches the bottom of the funnel opening. However, this stage significantly reduces the level of sound propagating through various media such as water, solids, and gases. So you can see that the sound has been reduced to the optimum level. After bubbling the water, it comes into contact with the baffle,

promoting turbulent flow of exhaust gases in and under the water surface without increasing back pressure. This improves engine efficiency. Baffles help reduce entrainment of water particles that are converted to steam. This also helps create a path for the exhaust. This is the main function of the baffle. A limestone tank above the baffle allows the exhaust gas to flow radially through the limestone. And this is the main part of the aqua silencer. Because there are some reactions going on. This helps remove toxic components of exhaust gases such as carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur oxides (SO_x) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). The fuel combustion products undergo a series of chemical reactions. The overall system area is larger than the engine's exhaust manifold outlet, which helps reduce system back pressure. The exhaust gases are then discharged from the engine as non-toxic gases.

VI. CHEMICAL REACTIONS

Alkaline solutions (lime water) are mainly used in scrubber tanks to dissolve unburned hydrocarbons (UBHC).

Chemical Reaction 1

The obnoxious product of combustion is NO_x— the oxides of Nitrogen. Water will absorb the oxides of Nitrogen to a larger extent.

Chemical Reaction 2

The lime water reacts with the diluted nitric and nitrous acids give calcium nitrate and calcium nitrite

Chemical Reaction 3

When the carbon-di-oxide present in the exhaust gas comes in contact with the limewater, calcium carbonate will precipitate.

Chemical Reaction 4

CO₂ will again combine with CaCO₃ to form calcium bicarbonate

Chemical Reaction 5

The sulphur-di-oxide present in the Diesel Exhaust also reacts with the limewater and calcium sulphite will precipitate.

Chemical Reaction 6

calcium carbonate, calcium sulphite will precipitate and CO₂ will be by-product.

Chemical Reaction 7

The presence of steam makes it possible to have a preliminary reaction with oxides of nitrogen, in the following manner;

The resultant products when comes in contact with calcium carbonate the following reaction takes place.

i.e., calcium Nitrate Ca(NO₃)₂ and calcium Nitrite Ca(NO₂)₂ are the by products, and CO₂ is liberated. The liberated CO₂ again combines with calcium carbonate to form calcium bicarbonate. Here all the toxic content can be reduced into the optimum level.

VII. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

A KIRLOSKER TV 1 diesel engine was chosen to test the Aqua muffler's noise and engine emissions

control. First, polluted, uncleaned engine exhaust was tested with the ORSAT device. The treated off-gas passing through the scrubber tank was then tested on the ORSAT apparatus. Observations of the ORSAT device before and after exhaust gas treatment are presented in two separate observation tables:

S.No.	% of load Applying	NOx (ppm)		Amount of PM (g/min)		Smoke Density (HSU)	
		With out AQUA Silencer	With AQUA Silencer	With out AQUA Silencer	With AQUA Silencer	With out AQUA Silencer	With AQUA Silencer
1	0	65.93	38.82	0.010	0.003	7.2	2.35
2	24.57	175.76	112.60	0.012	0.008	15.15	5.25
3	49.13	295.20	223.45	0.016	0.010	16.65	7.3
4	73.71	406.88	311.90	0.022	0.014	22.9	8.6
5	100	618.70	433.68	0.026	0.019	26.85	15.55

TABLE 1 RESULT TABULATION

FIG.6 BP vs SMOKE DENSITY

FIG.7 BP vs PARTICULATE MATTER

FIG. 8 BP vs NO_x

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The Aqua Muffler more effectively reduces emissions from the engine exhaust by using perforated pipes. The use of perforated pipe keeps the back pressure constant and reduces the noise level. When using perforated tubes, fuel consumption remains the same as in conventional systems. By using water as a medium, noise can be reduced, and by using activated carbon in water, emissions can be controlled at a higher level. Aqua muffler acidity is expected to be below dangerous acidity levels, so water contamination is negligible with the aqua muffler. i.e. 250 mg/liter. No smoke, no pollutants and very cheap. The performance of the aqua silencer is almost the same as the conventional silencer. By using an aqua silencer, NO_x is reduced to 29.9% and dust to 70% under no-load conditions. In smoke, the density is reduced to 67.36%.

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